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THERAPY**

2025, № 2 (Май)

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

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CURRENT ASPECTS OF THE DIAGNOSIS AND MODERN TREATMENT OF PLEURAL EMPYEMA

Rajabov Doston Uktamovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Republic of Uzbekistan, Bukhara

rajabov.doston@bsmi.uz

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4533-025X>

Abstract. In recent years, the rise in microbial resistance has altered the factors contributing to pleural empyema, creating a need to reassess treatment strategies. This review explores new treatment options for empyema, focusing on the use of advanced immunological and bronchological approaches, novel antiseptic agents, and endoscopic treatment methods.

Keywords: pleural empyema, pleural puncture, video-assisted thoracoscopy, fibrinolytic therapy.

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЭМПИЕМЫ ПЛЕВРЫ

Ражабов Достон Уктамович

Бухарский Государственный медицинский институт, Республика Узбекистан, Бухара

rajabov.doston@bsmi.uz

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4533-025X>

Аннотация. В последние годы, на фоне роста резистентности микрофлоры, изменились факторы, способствующие развитию эмпиемы плевры, что привело к необходимости пересмотра подходов к её лечению. В обзоре рассматриваются новые подходы в терапии эмпиемы, включающие использование современных иммунологических и бронхологических методов, а также новых антисептических средств и эндоскопических техник для лечения.

Ключевые слова: эмпиема плевры, плевральная пункция, видеоторакоскопия, фибринолитическая терапия.

PLEVRA EMPYEMASINI TASHXISLASH VA ZAMONAVIY DAVOLASHNING DOLZARB JIHATLARI

Annotatsiya. So'nggi yillarda mikroflora rezistentligining ortishi plevra empiyemasi rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ladigan omillar tarkibining o'zgarishiga olib keldi, bu esa kasallikni davolash usullarini qayta ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi. Ushbu sharhda zamonaviy immunologik, bronxologik yondashuvlar, yangi antiseptik vositalar va endoskopik davolash usullaridan foydalanish orqali plevra empiyemasini davolashda yuzaga kelgan yangi imkoniyatlar ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: plevra empiyemasi, plevra punksiyasi, videotorakoskopiya, fibrinolitik terapiya.

In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the number of patients presenting with purulent-destructive lung diseases, frequently complicated by pleural empyema. The term *pleural empyema* (or *pyothorax*) refers to a localized or diffuse inflammatory process involving the visceral and parietal pleura, characterized by the accumulation of pus in the pleural cavity and accompanied by symptoms of purulent intoxication.

In nearly 90% of cases, pleural empyema develops as a complication of inflammatory lung conditions—such as acute pneumonia (4%), lung abscesses (9–11%), and most notably, lung gangrene (80–95%) [2, 3]. Trauma to the chest accounts for 6–12% of cases, primarily due to unresolved post-traumatic pleuritis and hemothorax. Postoperative empyema represents 2–28% of cases and most often occurs following pneumonectomy. Complications in these cases are commonly due to fibrin deposits, blood clots in the pleural cavity, fragmentation into multiple small abscesses, and the presence of highly virulent aerobic bacteria in combination with non-spore-forming anaerobes.

Microbiological analysis reveals gram-positive bacteria in 30–40% of cases, predominantly *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Mixed infections involving non-clostridial anaerobes are observed in 20–30% of cases. Following surgical interventions, the pathogens most often isolated include aerobic gram-negative bacteria and *S. aureus*. Notably, in 5–20% of cases, the pleural exudate remains sterile.

According to current understanding of the pathogenesis, pleural empyema often develops following the rupture of one or more subpleurally located lung abscesses

into the pleural cavity, resulting in empyema accompanied by lung tissue destruction. If an intrapulmonary abscess connected to the bronchi ruptures into the pleural space, a pyopneumothorax may develop, sustained by the formation of bronchopleural fistulas. Less commonly, infection reaches the pleural cavity via lymphatic or hematogenous pathways. In such cases, pleural effusion may become purulent without evident necrotic lesions in the lung tissue.

Sometimes, empyema follows a slow, insidious course. The inflammation may gradually erode surrounding structures, including the chest wall. In such scenarios, purulent exudate may break into the bronchi or erode through the chest wall, extending beyond the pleural cavity. This can lead to the formation of abscesses between chest muscles or under the skin, which may eventually drain externally through the skin—a condition known as empyema necessitatis.

Most researchers recognize three distinct stages in the development of pleural empyema, each progressing into the next if untreated:

1. **Serous Stage:** The pleural cavity fills with a clear, serous exudate containing few polymorphonuclear leukocytes. This fluid is non-purulent and represents the initial inflammatory response.
2. **Purulent-Fibrinous Stage:** Microorganisms enter the pleural space—either directly, or via lymphatic or bloodborne routes—leading to infection of the exudate. Bacterial load increases, along with neutrophils and cellular debris. The fluid becomes turbid and overtly purulent. Fibrin layers begin to form on the parietal and visceral pleura, promoting the development of adhesions that compartmentalize the pleural space and lead to localized collections (intrapleural encapsulation). As fibrin, detritus, and desquamated epithelium accumulate, the exudate thickens and cannot be naturally reabsorbed.
3. **Fibrous Organization Stage:** Dense fibrous adhesions encase the lung, preventing its expansion. The lung tissue becomes immobilized and undergoes fibrotic transformation, leading to loss of function.

Classification of pleural empyemas (Kuzin M.I., 1976):

From an anatomical and morphological standpoint, pleural empyema is classified into two forms: **acute** and **chronic**. The condition is generally considered acute during the initial phase, lasting up to 8–12 weeks from disease onset. If the inflammatory process persists beyond 12 weeks, it is deemed **chronic**, indicating prolonged and progressive pleural involvement.

Based on the **extent of spread within the pleural cavity**, empyemas are categorized as follows:

1. **Free empyemas** – These are not confined by adhesions and may be:
 - Total (involving the entire pleural cavity),
 - Subtotal (involving a large portion),
 - Small (involving a limited area).

2. **Localized (encapsulated) empyemas** – These result from the formation of fibrous adhesions (moorings) that restrict the spread of purulent fluid.

Localized empyemas are further classified by **anatomical location**:

1. **Parietal (wall-adherent)** – Adjacent to the chest wall.
2. **Basal** – Situated between the diaphragm and the lower surface of the lung.
3. **Interlobar** – Found within the interlobar fissures.
4. **Apical** – Located at the apex of the lung.
5. **Paramediastinal** – Positioned near the mediastinum.
6. **Multiloculated (multi-chambered)** – Characterized by multiple isolated pus collections within the pleural cavity, separated by fibrous septa.

Empyemas are also classified based on their **communication with the external environment**:

1. **Closed empyemas** – Do not communicate with the external environment.
2. **Open empyemas** – Communicate through fistulous tracts, which may be:
 - **Pleuro-organic** (involving adjacent organs),
 - **Bronchopleural** (connecting to the bronchial tree),
 - **Pleurocutaneous** (opening through the skin).

Clinical picture

The clinical presentation of pleural empyema can vary, though all forms of acute empyema generally share a core set of symptoms: productive cough, shortness of breath, pleuritic chest pain that worsens with breathing, fever, and signs of systemic intoxication. In closed empyema, coughing typically produces only a small amount of sputum. However, frequent and intense coughing with copious purulent sputum often indicates the presence of a bronchopleural fistula.

Patients experiencing significant pain and dyspnea often adopt a semi-sitting posture, especially in total or subtotal empyemas, to ease respiratory effort. In contrast, with localized (encapsulated) or small empyemas, pain is usually milder. These patients may lie on the affected side, which limits chest wall movement on that side and helps reduce discomfort.

Physical examination of the chest typically reveals asymmetry in respiratory movement, with the affected side lagging. The intercostal spaces may appear widened and flattened due to internal pressure from the accumulated exudate.

When exudate accumulates in the pleural cavity, vocal fremitus and breath sounds over the area are diminished or absent. In cases where the cavity contains only fluid, the upper limit of dullness on percussion corresponds to the Ellis-Damoiseau-Sokolov line, which extends from the spine upward along the posterior axillary line and then descends anteriorly toward the midclavicular line. Large volumes of pus can cause mediastinal shift toward the healthy lung, compressing it. In such cases, a Grocco-Rauchfuss triangle—a triangular area of dull percussion sound—is noted on the healthy side, just below the spine.

In pyopneumothorax, percussion reveals a horizontal upper level of dullness (from pus accumulation) and a tympanic note above it (due to air). Auscultation may show markedly reduced or absent breath sounds and increased bronchophony over the fluid-filled area. If a bronchopleural fistula is present and the pleural cavity is effectively draining through the bronchi, amphoric (metallic) breath sounds may be heard—caused by air resonance in the large cavity. These patients often produce large volumes of foul-smelling purulent sputum.

As the disease progresses, pleural empyema often manifests as a severe systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS). Without prompt and appropriate treatment, it can lead to sepsis and eventually progress to multiple organ failure.

Diagnosis of acute pleural empyema

Laboratory indicators

The alterations in general clinical blood and urine parameters seen in **acute pleural empyema** are typically consistent with those observed in other severe purulent conditions. A **complete blood count** usually reveals **marked leukocytosis** (greater than $10 \times 10^9/L$), a **pronounced left shift** in the leukocyte differential, and an **elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR)**. **Anemia** is also commonly present.

In terms of biochemical changes, there is often a **reduction in plasma protein levels**, particularly due to a decrease in **albumin**. **Urinalysis** may show **albuminuria** along with the presence of **granular and hyaline casts**, reflecting the systemic inflammatory response.

X-ray diagnostics

X-ray examination is fundamental in the diagnosis of pleural empyema, providing valuable information about the location, extent, and volume of the pathological process within the pleural cavity. Advances in computer technology have significantly enhanced the accuracy, timeliness, and reliability of diagnostic imaging.

On X-ray images, pleural empyema typically appears as an area of increased opacity with an arcuate or oblique upper border. A large accumulation of pus causes a dense, homogeneous shadow over the affected hemithorax. This is often accompanied by a **mediastinal shift toward the healthy side**, downward displacement of the diaphragm, and loss of differentiation of the diaphragmatic dome. In cases of **localized parietal empyema**, the opacity appears semi-spindle-shaped with a broad base against the chest wall, and the inner border is convex, appearing to indent the lung. Limited empyemas located elsewhere in the pleural cavity may present with shadows of various shapes, including triangular or hemispherical.

When a **bronchopleural fistula** is present, air can accumulate in the pleural space, producing a visible horizontal fluid level that clearly demarcates the upper border of

the effusion. In some cases, contrast-enhanced X-ray studies, such as **bronchography** or **fistulography** (especially when an external fistula is suspected), are employed to improve diagnostic accuracy.

In addition to conventional radiography, **computed tomography (CT)** plays a crucial role in diagnosing pleural diseases. CT imaging provides detailed visualization of encapsulated effusions, pleural thickening, and focal pleural lesions, allowing for more precise assessment and treatment planning.

Ultrasound

Examination:

Ultrasound is a highly effective diagnostic tool due to its excellent resolution and real-time imaging capabilities. It is particularly valuable for detecting small volumes of pleural fluid—down to 100 ml—as well as assessing changes in the pleura and pleural cavity.

Pleural

Puncture:

Pleural puncture is an essential procedure when evaluating patients with pleural empyema. It allows for the characterization of the pleural fluid and facilitates bacteriological examination to identify the causative microorganisms and determine their antibiotic sensitivities. The procedure is performed under local anesthesia, with the patient seated. The puncture site is typically located in the 6th to 7th intercostal space, between the scapular and midaxillary lines. Ultrasound guidance is preferred to optimize accuracy and safety. Fluid obtained from the puncture is always sent for microscopic examination and biochemical analysis.

Treatment:

Despite advances in antibacterial medications and modern surgical techniques, the management of acute pleural empyema remains a significant clinical challenge. The primary treatment approach continues to be **drainage of the pleural cavity**, combined with continuous aspiration and lavage of the empyema space.

Some experts consider the **presence of purulent pleural fluid** as a clear indication for drainage. However, relying solely on neutrophil count or protein levels in the pleural fluid is insufficient to determine the need for this procedure.

Biochemical markers of the pleural fluid provide more reliable guidance: when **glucose levels exceed 60 mg/dL** or **pH is above 7.3**, favorable outcomes can often be achieved with antibacterial therapy alone. Conversely, a **glucose concentration below 40 mg/dL**, **pH under 7.1**, and elevated **lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)** levels indicate a strong need for pleural drainage.

For cases with intermediate glucose or pH values, treatment decisions become more complex. In such situations, the indication for drainage should be based on the patient's **clinical response to antibiotic therapy** and findings from **repeat pleural fluid analyses**.

Ya. G. Kolkin et al. (2006) advocate for combining pleural drainage with active aspiration techniques and temporary bronchial occlusion in patients with bronchopleural fistulas. This combined approach reportedly achieved positive results in approximately 90.5% of cases.

Most authors, particularly domestic experts, recommend beginning treatment of **postoperative empyema** with **pleural punctures** using one or two needles, followed by drainage with double- or triple-lumen tubes and repeated irrigation of the pleural cavity with antiseptic solutions—sometimes for periods lasting 3 to 6 weeks. This approach often leads to the development of fibrothorax. If conservative measures fail, L.V. Uspensky and colleagues utilize **open repeated sanitation of the pleural cavity** assisted by ultrasound, which generates H and OH ions. These ions alter the redox state of microorganisms, promoting their destruction.

According to P. Wong and P. Goldstraw (1994), in cases of postoperative empyema **without bronchial fistula, rib resection** combined with prolonged drainage (3 to 12 months) of the pleural cavity is advised [18]. D. Schneiter et al. (2001) advocate for **radical surgery** as the optimal treatment. This involves breaking down septations and daily tamponade of the pleural space with antiseptic solutions until the cavity is macroscopically clean. On average, 3.5 interventions were needed (ranging from 3 to 5), with an average hospital stay of 17 days.

When drainage via the intercostal approach is insufficient, and the empyema becomes organized with pleural thickening and lung compression, **surgical intervention** becomes necessary. In such cases, **open thoracotomy and decortication** are recommended, particularly during the third stage of empyema and in infections caused by anaerobic bacteria, Staphylococcus, or pneumococci [20]. However, decortication is technically challenging and carries risks of lung damage. For some patients, it may be contraindicated or poorly tolerated, necessitating continuation of conservative treatment.

Therapeutic Videopleuroscopy (Thoracoscopy):

Therapeutic videopleuroscopy has been effectively used to re-expand the collapsed lung during the third stage of empyema. This procedure involves the destruction of loose adhesions and the removal of fibrin deposits from the visceral pleura's surface. Additionally, ultrasound or plasma sanitation of the pleural cavity is often performed during the intervention.

According to O.O. Yasnogorodsky et al. (2004), the primary indication for video-assisted thoracoscopic sanitation in empyema is failure of fractional lavage after two weeks or the inability to adequately sanitize the pleural cavity due to a bronchopleural fistula when the disease duration is less than one month. The authors emphasize that video-assisted thoracoscopic sanitation is most effective in **acute pleural empyema** before the formation of a fibrous scar layer. Once the disease progresses to the **chronic stage**, thorough sanitation is achievable only through open surgery, such as mini-thoracotomy or traditional thoracotomy.

However, the timeframe defining the transition from acute to chronic pleural empyema is somewhat arbitrary, ranging from one month up to 8–12 months. G.I. Lukomsky (1976) proposed that differentiation between acute and chronic empyema should be based on **morphological changes in the visceral pleura**, which influence the lung's ability to re-expand and thus guide treatment choices. The rigidity of the visceral pleura and the strength of connective tissue adhesions determine this transition, making it impossible to define chronic inflammation strictly by calendar timeframes.

The use of **videothoracoscopy** in treating pleural empyema minimizes surgical trauma, significantly reduces postoperative complications, and shortens hospital stays. This method is usually effective in the early stages of the disease but may be unsuccessful when extensive pleural adhesions are present. In such cases, **thoracotomy and decortication** become necessary. Although these open surgeries have a high success rate (>90%), they carry considerable surgical risk, especially for debilitated patients. **Open drainage** with rib resection is generally considered a less favorable option and is reserved for patients who cannot tolerate more invasive procedures.

According to T. Simmers et al., in cases of **parapneumonic effusion**, thoracocentesis combined with pleural cavity lavage should be performed in all patients except those with small hydrothorax. Experimental studies on rabbits demonstrated that daily thoracocentesis is more effective in inducing acute pleural empyema than pleural cavity drainage [26]. Domestic surgeons A.N. Kabanov, L.A. Sitko, and V.I. Maslov recommend starting empyema treatment with pleural puncture, which is considered the gentlest method.

P.P. Kurlaev (2001) treats acute suppurative diseases of the lungs and pleura, including empyema, by using pleural puncture with copious lavage of the cavity with antiseptic solutions, followed by the administration of a single dose of antibiotic and 5 ME oxytocin, which significantly enhances the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy [29]. E.A. Tseimakh et al. (2009) suggest that punctures should be limited to 4–5 days, after which drainage should be initiated to prevent chest wall phlegmon—a complication occurring in 7.8% of cases [30]. However, N.N.

Kosolobov et al. (2000) note that chest wall phlegmon is more frequently associated with drainage than with puncture 31.

A significant role in the treatment of acute pleural empyema today is played by the introduction of **fibrinolytics** into the pleural cavity. This approach targets the many small sequestered cavities and fibrinous partitions that form, which hinder thorough local sanitation. The most commonly used fibrinolytic agents are **streptokinase** and **urokinase**. S. Schiza et al. (2005) reported positive outcomes when administering intrapleural streptokinase combined with streptodornase-alpha to patients.

S. Sahn (2003) compared patients treated with intrapleural streptokinase against a control group that received only saline. The treated group experienced shorter hospital stays, improved local treatment outcomes, better radiographic resolution, increased drainage volume, and a 100% success rate with conservative therapy. However, a similar study by R. Cameron (2004) involving 58 patients found no significant differences in treatment duration, radiographic improvement, or the need for surgery between streptokinase and control groups. Cameron suggested that further studies with larger patient numbers were necessary. Laboratory studies showed that neither streptokinase nor urokinase reduced pus viscosity, indicating their effect mainly involved breaking down intracavitary fibrinous septa rather than altering pus properties.

According to E. Herrejon (2009), the effectiveness of fibrinolytic therapy may be overstated. A large double-blind randomized trial in the UK involving 454 patients with purulent pleurisy compared intrapleural streptokinase (250,000 IU twice daily for 3 days) to placebo. The study found no reduction in mortality or surgical intervention rates: 31% in the streptokinase group versus 27% in the placebo group. Streptokinase did not improve treatment outcomes or shorten hospital stays. Moreover, serious adverse events were more frequent in the streptokinase group (7%) compared to placebo (3%). Based on these findings, the author advised against the routine use of intrapleural streptokinase for purulent pleurisy treatment.

Thanks to complex therapy, the effectiveness of treating acute purulent-destructive diseases of the lungs and pleura can be significantly improved, leading to fewer severe complications and reducing the risk of progression to chronic disease. However, research by A.M. Sukhorukov et al. (2005) revealed that many patients already exhibit varying degrees of secondary immunodeficiency upon hospital admission. Additionally, antibiotics—particularly those from the penicillin group—can decrease the activity of complement proteins in the blood serum. Although traditional antibacterial treatment for pleural empyema may result in clinical recovery and pathogen elimination, the underlying immune deficiency is not resolved and may even worsen. As a result, the infectious process can persist. To enhance immune function, extracorporeal therapy with immunofan was used alongside antibiotics, which helped to restore and optimize patients' immune status.

Currently, the optimal method for sanitizing the empyema cavity remains unresolved, as it depends on the different stages of the inflammatory process in the pleural cavity and requires careful laboratory monitoring of treatment effectiveness. Several researchers recommend rinsing the pleural cavity with antiseptic solutions such as furacilin, boric acid, iodinol, chlorhexidine, and others. R. Agarwal and A. Aggarwal (2006) demonstrated the effectiveness of using 10% iodopovidone during thoracostomy in patients with acute pleural empyema, although they did not assess the impact of this treatment on the immune status.

G.I. Lukomsky found that with adequate drainage combined with fractional lavage and continuous active aspiration, there was no significant difference between using simple boiled water and commonly applied antiseptics like furacilin or chlorhexidine within the pleural cavity.

E.A. Tseimakh emphasizes that treatment of pleural empyema and pyopneumothorax should be comprehensive, including targeted correction of the functional state of proteolytic systems and phagocytes both in the blood and the pleural cavity. This can be achieved through cryoplasma-antienzyme complexes, plasmapheresis, plasma leukophoresis, and drugs that regulate the metabolic, coagulation, and proteolytic activity of phagocytes at the inflammation site, as well as local proteolysis inhibitors and activators tailored to various phases of inflammation. This complex therapeutic approach has reduced mortality from the disease by 2.3 times and increased the number of patients discharged with recovery by 1.5 times.

Acute purulent-destructive conditions in the organs of the chest cavity cause severe endogenous intoxication, which leads to high mortality rates and draws medical attention to various extracorporeal detoxification methods, including plasmapheresis. Existing literature reports on the use of extracorporeal detoxification in patients with sepsis. However, the success of plasmapheresis depends heavily on properly replenishing the removed plasma with donor plasma and protein products (such as albumin, protein, or alvezin). Currently, this full correction is challenging due to donor plasma shortages and carries risks such as anaphylactic reactions and infections. Additionally, although exchange plasmapheresis effectively detoxifies the body, it has drawbacks: it lacks immunostimulatory effects and removes immunoglobulins, leukocytes, and erythrocytes along with toxic plasma.

Therefore, many challenges remain unresolved in treating acute nonspecific pleural empyema. Each treatment method has its own advantages and disadvantages, and there are virtually no absolute guidelines for choosing a specific approach. Intrapleural administration of antiseptic solutions often proves ineffective in some cases, prolonging treatment and contributing to the progression to chronic stages. At present, the issue of how to best sanitize the empyema cavity, depending on the phase of inflammation and based on laboratory monitoring of treatment efficacy, remains unsettled.

Minimally invasive thoracoscopic procedures offer clear benefits, yet the criteria for their use need further clarification and broader definition as treatment for pleural empyema evolves.

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